
Development Finance and the Productivity of Agricultural Sector in Nigeria

By

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of development finance on the productivity of agricultural sector in Nigeria. Time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin from 1990-2023. Productivity of agricultural was modeled as the function of Agricultural Grantee scheme as percentage of gross domestic product, Microcredit from microfinance banks as percentage of gross domestic product, Agricultural development Bank finance of gross domestic product, Bank of industry finance of gross domestic product and Commercial bank credit to agricultural sector of gross domestic product. Multiple regressions were formulated. Unit Root test, co-integration, granger causality and Vector Error Correction model was used. The study found the variables were stationary at difference, presence long run and uni-directional causality from agricultural credit grantee scheme to agricultural productivity. The variables were found to have positive effect on agricultural productivity except commercial banks credit. From the findings, we concluded that development finance as modeled in the study have significant effect on agricultural productivity. We recommended Government should continually increase the funding and operation of the agriculture credit guarantee scheme fund, reduction of monetary policy rate on the agricultural sector and that Central Bank of Nigeria should mandate commercial bank to set aside a certain amount of money from their yearly profit to finance agriculture.

Keywords: Development Finance, Productivity, Agricultural Sector, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is an important sector of the economy with high potential for employment generation, food security and poverty reduction. Although the sector was largely dominated by subsistence farming, with improved seedlings, modern farming methods and better weather forecasting, agricultural yields have continued to grow. Nigeria has an arable land area of 34 million hectares: 6.5 million hectares for permanent crops, and 28.6 million hectares for meadows and pastures (Osabohien, Osabuohien & Ohalet. 2019a). The country has historically been a leading producer of palm oil, cocoa beans, pineapple, and sorghum (Okafor, 2020). The sector's contribution to GDP in FY'21 was 25.88%, second to the service sector and affirming its position as a key sector in the Nigerian economy (Ellah & Emeh, 2020). With the increasing population, estimated to reach 400 million by 2050, enhancing productivity in agriculture through the adaptation of new technologies and innovations is necessary to ensure food security and good nutrition.

To maintain its share of the continent's agriculture GDP by 2030, Nigeria will need to grow its agriculture sector revenues by a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.7% annually. To ensure this is achieved, agriculture budget to GDP will have to be sustained by at least 7% annually. It is estimated that agriculture is Africa's largest economic sector, representing 15% of the continent's total GDP (Osabohien, Mordi & Ogundipe, 2020). Nigeria contributes 14% of Africa's agriculture GDP. The World Bank forecasts that by 2030, the food market in Africa will grow to be a US\$1 trillion industry. Nigeria will need to intensify its investments in improving agriculture yield and integrating the value-chain over the next decade to effectively capture a significant share of the US\$1 trillion market (Osabohien, Ufua, Moses & Osabuohien, 2020c). According to the Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA), Africa continent would require over US\$300 billion of public and private investments across the agriculture value-chain over the next decade.

Nigeria's agriculture contribution to GDP makes it the largest sector in the country. Crop production accounts for a huge chunk of activities in the sector representing 88% of total industry size with livestock, forestry and fishing accounting for the balance of 12%. The sector achieved GDP of US\$113.64 billion in 2014, the highest in the last five years (2013 – 2017). Since then, the sector's contribution has been declining due to low agriculture yields, conflicts such as terrorism and the herdsman crisis, as well as the impact of climate change (Chisasa & Nakina, 2015; Udoka, Mbat, & Duke, 2016).

Agriculture contribution to Nigeria's GDP dropped by 31% from US\$113.64 billion in 2013 to US\$78.45 billion in 2017, Food import bill in 2017 was US\$4.5 billion representing a 12.2% increase from the 2016 bill of US\$4.01 billion. However, Q2 2018 bill of US\$0.97 billion shows a decline of 31% over Q1 2018 import bill of US\$1.4 billion. Though Q2 2018 bill of US\$0.97 billion reflected a decline of 31% over Q1 2018 bill of US\$1.4 billion, when compared to Q2 2017 of US\$0.48 billion, it was a significant increase of 102%. Nigeria is the largest rice producing country in West Africa (Ezu, 2023). In addition, the country grows about 50% of grain crops produced in West Africa. Nigeria is the 3rd largest millet producing country in the world after India and China (Saka, Akinde, & Afolabi, 2023). Also, the country is the world largest producer of cassava and yam; the 2nd world largest producer of sweet potatoes and the 4th world largest producer of groundnut and cocoa.

Nigeria has over 84 million hectares of arable land, of which only about 40% is cultivated; 230 billion cubic metres of water; abundant and reliable rainfall in over two-thirds of its

territory, and some of the richest natural resources for agricultural production in the world. The ratio of Nigeria's budget for agriculture to annual budget falls short of the prescribed standard set by the Maputo Declaration on Agriculture and Food Security ("The declaration"). Through the declaration, the African Union (AU) agreed to allocate at least 10% of its member countries annual national budget to agriculture, budgetary allocation for agriculture of N0.20 trillion accounts for 2.2% of the proposed 2018 budget of N9.12 trillion (Saka, Akinde, & Afolabi, 2023). In 2017, agriculture budget of N0.10 trillion represented 1.3% of total budget of N7.44 trillion. Agricultural activities nevertheless are typically concentrated in less developed rural areas where rural transformation, redistribution, poverty reduction, and socio-economic development are vital. Between 2010 and 2016, the GDP to agricultural output increased by 1.15 percent, from \$8.287 million to \$17.879 million. Nigeria's agriculture industry contributed 2.26 percent of GDP in 2019 (CBN 2019). In the second quarter of 2023, the agricultural sector generated about 21 percent of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product. The largest contribution was from crop production, which covered nearly 19 percent of the GDP.

Finance has been identified as a major factor hindering agriculture production, for this reason various programmes, policies as well as institutions have been established with the aim of providing easy finance to the sector of which Deposit Money Banks has been at the forefront for this purpose. One of the major inputs identified over the years in the development of the Nigerian agricultural sector has been the agricultural credit (CBN, 2022). The sources for funding the agricultural sector have been micro and macro sources of finance. The micro source relates the use of the deposit money bank financing as capital for agricultural activities while agricultural funding through capital mobilization and allocation by government through such agencies as rural banking development programmes, Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative and Rural development Bank (NACRDB) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) are the macro source of agricultural financing.

Despite the abolition of the mandatory sectoral credit allocation, agricultural sector and its lending remain a priority to the government, thereby making it an investment outlet to financial institutions (Orok & Ayim, 2017). Apart from the deposit money banks, government established institutions and program play a major role in financing the Agric sector in Nigeria. Example, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has a department for Agricultural finance, the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme, the Nigerian agricultural credit bank and the new reformed microfinance banks. In Nigeria, apart from monetary policy of the government, agricultural lending is the function of economic environment, the rate of return, the growth of agricultural industries and the political interest of the government to agricultural sector (Anyanwu *et al.*, 1997).

The Nigeria agriculture sector is still manifesting physical symptoms of peasant agriculture. It is dominated by small scale farmers who are responsible for about 95% of total production i.e. the bulk of the source of our food. The livestock is in the hands of nomadic herdsmen; poultry is still essentially the backyard type; though a few commercial units are here and there. The fishing sector is also predominantly artisanal; very few motorized canoes are in use not to talk of fishing trawlers. However, despite the need and importance of agriculture in supply of food, creation of employment and provision of raw material to industries, financial institutions do not consider it important in financing Agricultural sector due to the high risk of loan default and the long-term nature of Agricultural loans. The compliance rate to Agricultural lending is very poor compared to other sectors of the economy such as the industrial sector (Osiegbu, 2005). From the above, this study examined development finance and agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agriculture Finance

Agriculture finance can be defined as various funds set aside to strengthen farming business in Nigeria and improve people's socio-economic welfare. It includes both government money and non-governmental groups working toward sector growth, economic empowerment, and social empowerment. Adejumo and Bolarinwa (2017) hypothesized agricultural financing programs as part of financial arrangements set up by the government at all levels to assist farmers' access to finance and invariably boost agricultural productivity.

Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF): The ACGSF was created in 1987 by Decree No. 20 and began activities in April 1978. It commenced with N100 million in share capital and N85.6 million in paid-up capital. The Federal Ministry of Finance owns 60% of the stock, while the Central Bank of Nigeria owns 40% (CBN 2019). The capital base of the scheme as of March 2001 was N3 billion and then N50 billion in March 2019 under the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Amendment Act. Bank loan facilities extended to farmers are guaranteed by the Fund up to 75% of the amount in default, net of any security realized. The Central Bank of Nigeria is in charge of the Scheme's day-to-day operations and fund management.

Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Corporation: It was founded in 1987 to protect Nigerian farmers against risk. Due to its unique socio-economic benefits to the public, it is also the only existing insurance firm controlled by the federal government. The reason is that it covers the areas of traditional insurers' inability to handle agricultural risks, which they deemed too risky. The Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Corporation (NAIC) has a wide goal of protecting Nigerian farmers from the consequences of natural disasters by enacting policies that assure quick payment of adequate indemnity (compensation) to keep farmers in business after a loss.

National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND): The Federal Government established NERFUND in 1989 to provide short, medium, and long-term financing for wholly Nigerian-owned SMEs in manufacturing, agro-allied enterprises, mining, quarrying, industrial support services, equipment leasing, and other ancillary projects. Between 1989 and 1995, NERFUND funded 474 initiatives, but just 87 projects were approved between 1996 and 1998. NERFUND disbursed approximately \$144.9 million and \$681.5 million to eligible projects from its creation through 1998 (CBN, 2014).

Bank Credit

Agricultural credit is expected to play a critical role in agricultural development (Duong and Izumida, 2002). Farm credit has for long been identified as a major input in the development of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. The decline in the contribution of the sector to the Nigeria economy has been attributed to the lack of a formal national credit policy and paucity of credit institutions, which can assist farmers among other things. The provision of this input is important because credit or loanable fund (capital) is viewed as more than just another resource such as labour, land, equipment and raw materials. It determines access to all of the resources on which farmers depend (Shephard, 1979). Agricultural sector is situated within the framework of the rural economy and the financial markets. A key feature of the sector is the dominance of small holding farm families, rural households, agricultural households, or farm households. They cultivate less than five hectares hence, they look insignificant individually but collectively they form the foundation on which the nation's economy rests (Falusi, 1995).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical concept of this study is centred on the Theory of Financial Intermediation. Financial institutions, as explained by Shaw (1973) and Mickinnon (1973), are a channel through which huge amounts of credit are available for spontaneous economic expansion. This theory was shown as the supply-leading role of financial institutions. Robison (2001) stated that the theory specifically postulates rural economic growth with an emphasis on agricultural financing. The implication is that the financial sector provides upfront loans for farm products through subsidized credits and other agricultural inputs. The hypothesis took into account the limitations farmers, growers, and tillers encounter in obtaining farm inputs and other agricultural implements, as well as bank interest while Robison (1952) argued that finance is a handmaid to economic expansion, that increase in productivity promotes the demand for the financial instrument.

Empirical Review

Mbelu and Ifionu (2022) examined the influence of agricultural financing on economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1981 to 2019. The objective of the study is to the impact of the long-term relationship between various forms of agricultural financing on Nigeria's economic growth. The study employs the stationary test, the co-integration test, the error correction model and the Granger causality model. All variables were stationary at the first difference, and the co-integration test evidenced a long-run relationship. The study identified, in the long run, that; the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund shows a positive and significant influence on the gross domestic product in Nigeria. The commercial bank loan and community –micro-finance bank loan shows a positive and significant influence on the gross domestic product in Nigeria within the reference period. In light of the findings, the study concluded that all the variables employed predict Nigeria's gross domestic product. Furthermore, the granger causality results show a demand following a role as against supply leading role, revealing that increase in output level in Nigeria significantly support/promotes agricultural financial instrument.

Olatunji et al. (2018) explored the restructuring of the rural finance market in Nigeria for agricultural expansion from 1996Q1 -2017Q4. The study adopted Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds testing approach in estimating the relevant relationship. The results of the long-run estimate showed that agricultural credit, money markets, capital markets, and exchange rates have a positive relationship with agricultural growth in Nigeria, while expected inflation has a negative impact on agricultural growth in the long run. Enoma (2010) observed that in Nigeria, agricultural finance, interest rates, and exchange rates stimulate output from the evaluation of the impact of agriculture credit on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986-2007. The study utilized ordinary least square techniques for data analysis. The interest rate, exchange rate, and agricultural credit were the study's variables.

Egwu (2016) evaluated the effectiveness of agricultural financing on agricultural output, economic growth, and poverty reduction in Nigeria. T-test, R-square, Standard Error Test, and Durbin Watson test ADF/PP unit root and co-integration test were utilized for data analysis. The empirical findings demonstrated that Commercial Bank Credit to the Agricultural Sector (CBCA) and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund Loans to Nigeria's Agricultural Sector (ACGSF) indicated significant in Agricultural Sector Output as a Percentage of GDP (ASOGDP). Based on the findings, the study advocates that the government should implement policies that encourage agricultural commercialization, such as cooperatives, agricultural subsidies, and zero-tariff agricultural input imports. Oyeronke and Bolarinwa (2017) used descriptive statistics for data analysis in assessing the performance of the agricultural credit guarantee scheme funds in Nigeria from 1981 to 2016.

The variables employed are agricultural credit deployed to the geo-political zones viz North Central, North East, North West, South East, South-South and South West. The findings show that only 21.4 percent of the total number of farmers has access to ACGSF loans. In addition, the majority of the credit fund is allocated to food crop cultivation. The study suggests that agricultural policies be improved in order to establish a favourable and enabling environment for farmers, particularly small-scale farmers, to obtain finance. Omosebi and Aladejana (2016) viewed the capacity of agricultural credit to Nigeria's economy from 1986-2014. The variables were assessed using a stationary test, cointegration test, modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) and Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach. Credit to the agriculture sector, exchange rate, interest rate, private domestic investment, inflation rate, and economic growth in Nigeria were all used in the study. The findings revealed that agricultural finance and economic growth have a strong short- and long-term correlation. However, control variables such as the real exchange rate and private domestic investment had a direct impact on economic development, whereas the inflation rate had an inverse association in the model. Therefore, canvass for more credit to the sector so as to facilitate the growth of the economy. Adetiloye (2012) assessed the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) in Nigeria for food security (1978-2006). The study centred on secondary data from the Nigerian Central Bank's (CBN) statistical bulletin. Agricultural credit from Deposit Money Banks claims filed, and claims settled are among the study's variables. The study used t-tests and paired t-tests and the Granger Causality test. The study found credit to the agric sector has a positive effect on economic productivity but is inconsequential to the economy in terms of growth, whereas ACGSF indicated an adverse performance on economic growth. The test on food security showed negative results in Nigeria as food insecurity is widespread. As a result, it is suggested that government should make agriculture more attractive so as to encourage the youth to harp into the value chain.

Tiamiyu et al. (2017) evaluated the role of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund, commercial bank loans to agriculture, and agriculture's percentage of GDP from 1981-2017. Correlation Matrix and Ordinary Least Square regression were used as statistical approaches. Agricultural credit, interest rates, and exchange rates equally drive output in Nigeria, as shown in the empirical findings. Ali et al. (2016) attempted to estimate the connection between financial intermediation through deposit money banks and agricultural growth for the period 1981 to 2014. For data analysis, the ordinary least square approach, Unit root, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), and Heteroskedasticity White Test were employed although the conclusion for Deposit Money Banks' lending rate (DMBLR) suggested a negative and minimal impact on Agricultural production, the study demonstrated that deposit money banks' credit is significant for output leap in the agricultural sector (AQ). Nnamdi and Torbira (2015) evaluated the nature of the interrelationship between micro credits allocations to classified sectors of the economic environment and gross domestic product in Nigeria from (1992-2014). The study utilized Augmented Dickey-fuller, Johansen's co-integration, Error correction model and standard pairwise granger causality tests. The findings centred on no significant relationship between Nigeria's gross domestic product and micro-credit allocation to agriculture/forestry, mining, and quarrying, however, there is a positive and significant relationship between Nigeria's gross domestic product and micro-credit allocation to manufacturing/food processing, as well as real estate/construction. The causality flows from gross domestic product to micro-credit allocations to that sector. Nwakamma et al. (2014) discovered a considerable long-run relationship between Nigeria's gross domestic product and micro-credit distribution. While the granger causality indicated a demand following role which run from economic growth to micro credits (unidirectional). However, it is suggested

that the number of microcredit products be increased in order to accelerate microcredit's contribution to Nigeria's economic growth.

Medugui et al. (2019) employed the ordinary least square method to assess the role of Commercial Banks' credit on Agricultural output in Nigeria, covering the period 1980 to 2018. The results revealed that commercial bank credit as well as government expenditure on agriculture predicts output level in Nigeria. The interest rate was inversely associated with agricultural output; the results were completely consistent with a priori expectations. Thus, the regulatory authority should establish policies that will encourage commercial banks to reduce their interest rates so as to make more funds available to farmers at affordable rates, and increase their expenditure in agriculture with strict compliance monitoring while for the period 1992Q1-2015Q4. Fintan and Lema (2018) analyzed the short and long-run connections between government expenditure on agriculture, bank loans to agriculture, and Tanzania's gross domestic product for the period 1990-2016. Ordinary least square techniques were used for data analysis. The empirical data revealed that the variables used have a notable short and long-run link. In light of further evidence, the study concluded that positive agricultural funding shocks have a substantial impact on economic growth. The study recommends that government funding for agriculture should be increased.

Michael (2016) adopted a survey research design for data collection and analysis of 105 farmers in the Ogun State to evaluate the impact of financial inclusion in the agriculture sector. The finding showed that financial inclusion in the Nigerian agriculture sector is vital for sustainable development. Therefore, recommend more establishments of rural banking institutions in primitive areas, and stimulates financial discipline among others so as to promote financial inclusion in the agricultural sector. Okunlola et al. (2019) used stepwise regression analysis techniques on time series data over a 36-year period (1970-2009) to test the effects of agricultural guaranteed finance on the economic growth of Nigeria in the farm products such as oil palm, cocoa, groundnuts, fishery, poultry, cattle, roots, and tubers. The data was taken from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin. From the empirical analysis, 81 percent of root and tuber, 87 percent of cocoa, and 90 percent of chicken have a reasonable and statistically significant influence on Nigeria's economic growth.

Saka, Akindeand Afolabi (2023) investigated the short-run dynamics and long-run link between credit financing offered by Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) and agricultural development in Nigeria for a period of 1981 to 2020. A quantitative ex-post facto research design was employed to analyze bank credit impact on agricultural advancement at both aggregate and sub-sectoral agricultural production. The research strategy utilized allows the use of economic series obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2021) and World Bank Development Indicators (2021) to be analyzed by Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique. From ARDL estimations, it is indicated that DMBs loans and advances have significantly negative short-run impacts on agricultural development in Nigeria at both aggregate and sub-sector levels. However, Bounds Testing analysis shows that the impacts of DMBs financing on Nigeria agriculture sector and labour employment in the sector become positively significant over a long period at aggregate level and for crop production only as a sub-sector. But the observed positive long-run impact of DMBs lending to agriculture was not significant for advancement of other subsectors (livestock, fishing and forestry). Hence, the study affirms that in the short run DMBs lending significantly slow down agricultural development in Nigeria but increases it significantly in the long run. Osabohien et al., (2020) employed ARDL technique to analyse data drawn for a period between 1981 to 2018 from CBN Bulletin and World Bank Development Indicators. The

findings from the study indicate that increased access to bank credit facilities significantly and positively improve the performance of Nigeria agricultural sector in the long run.

Ezu(2023) examined the impact of agricultural financing on the growth of Nigerian economy. The specific objective of the study is to examine the impact of Bank of Agriculture loan to farmers on gross domestic product; assess the impact of commercial banks credit to agriculture on gross domestic product and evaluate the impact of agriculture credit guarantee scheme fund on gross domestic product. Secondary data was used for data collection. This research work applied Ordinary least square; the Granger Causality Test, and Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test. The result of the finding shows that Bank of Agriculture credit to farmers as well as Commercial banks credit to agriculture showed a significant relationship to Gross Domestic product. There is a positive and statistically significant relationship between agriculture credit guarantee scheme fund and gross domestic product.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quasi-experimental research design and econometric methodology to evaluate the long-term relationship between development finance and productivity of agricultural sector in Nigeria. The study employed a stationarity test; Johansen co-integration test, Error correction model and granger causality test were applied.

Model Specification

$$AP = f(ACGS, MC, ADB, BI, CB) \quad (1)$$

$$AP = \beta + \beta_1 ACGS + \beta_2 MC + \beta_3 ADB + \beta_4 BI + \beta_5 CB + e_i \quad (2)$$

Where

AP = Agricultural productivity proxy by contribution agricultural sector to gross domestic product

ACGS = Agricultural Grantee scheme as percentage of gross domestic product

MC = Microcredit from microfinance banks as percentage of gross domestic product

ADB = Agricultural development Bank finance of gross domestic product

BI = Bank of industry finance of gross domestic product

CB = Commercial bank credit to agricultural sector of gross domestic product

β = regression intercept

e_i = Error term

Method of Data Analysis

Stationarity test: The stationarity test is necessary to measure the unit root properties of the time series. Furthermore, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is employed. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis if the ADF test statistics is absolutely higher than Mackinnon's critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance (Brooks, 2009). Johansen's co-integration test: This test is used to ascertain the extent and level of long-run equilibrium relationship between employed study variables (Awe, 2012). The decision rule is based on significance at the .05level, of the co-integrating equation.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is used. The ADF test simply runs a regression of the first-difference of the series against a first-lagged value, constant, and a time trend as the following:

$$\text{Without Intercept and Trend } DY_t = d Y_{t-1} + U_t \quad (3)$$

$$\text{With Intercept } DY_t = a + d Y_{t-1} + U_t \quad (4)$$

$$\text{With Intercept and Trend } DY_t = a + bT + d Y_{t-1} + U_t \quad (5)$$

Decision rule:

Decision rule:

If $t^* >$ ADF critical value, \implies do not reject null hypothesis, i.e., unit root exists.

If $t^* <$ ADF critical value, \implies reject null hypothesis, i.e., unit root does not exist.

The test for a unit root is a test on the coefficient of (Y_{t-1}) in the regression. If the ADF test-statistic (t-statistic) is less (in the absolute value) than the Mackinnon critical t-values, the null hypothesis of a unit root cannot be rejected for the time series and hence, one can conclude that the series is non-stationary at their levels (Engle & Granger, 1987). The unit root test tests for the existence of a unit root in three cases: without intercept and trend, with intercept only and with intercept and trend to take into the account the impact of the trend on the series (Engle & Granger, 1987). variables have a long-run relationship in a bivariate framework.

Testing for Cointegration Using Johansen's Test

Johansen's methodology takes its starting point in the vector auto regression (VAR) of order p given by

$$y_t = \mu + A_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + A_{p-1} y_{t-p+1} + \delta \tau \quad (6)$$

Where y_t is an $n \times 1$ vector of variables that are integrated of order one – commonly denoted $I(1)$ – and τ is an $n \times 1$ vector of innovations. This VAR can be re-written as

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \alpha y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (7)$$

where

$$\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^p A_i - I \text{ and } \alpha_1 = - \sum_{i=1}^p A_i \quad (8)$$

If the coefficient matrix Π has reduced rank $r < n$, then there exist $n \times r$ matrices α and β each with rank r such that $\Pi = \alpha\beta'$ and $\beta'y_t$ is stationary. R is the number of cointegrating relationships, the elements of α are known as the adjustment parameters in the error correction model and each column of β is a cointegrating vector. It can be shown that for a given r , the maximum likelihood estimator of β defines the combination of y_{t-1} that yields the r largest canonical correlations of Δy_t with y_{t-1} after correcting for lagged difference and deterministic variables when present. Johansen proposes two different likelihood ratio tests of the significance of these canonical correlations and thereby the reduced rank of the Π matrix: the trace test and maximum Eigen value test, shown in equations (7) and (8) respectively.

$$\int \text{trace} \quad r \sum_{r-1}^m m(1 A1) \quad (9)$$

$$\int \text{trace} = T \ln(1 - \lambda_r + 1) \quad (10)$$

Here T is the sample size and λ_i is the largest canonical correlation. The trace test tests the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of n cointegrating vectors. The maximum Eigen value test, on the other hand, test the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of $r+1$ cointegrating vectors. Neither of these test statistics follows a chi square distribution in general; asymptotic critical values can be found in (Johansen & Juselius, 1990) and are also given by most econometric software

packages. Since the critical values used for the maximum Eigen value and trace test statistics are based on a pure unit-root assumption, they will no longer be correct when the variables in the system are near unit-root processes. Thus, the real question is how sensitive Johansen's procedures are to deviations from the pure unit root assumption.

Error Correction Model: According to Brooks (2009), tend to assess the long-run sensitivity of dependent variables to each of the explanatory variables. It more accurately estimates the time it takes for the dependent variable to return to long-run equilibrium following short-term distortions in the explanatory factors. Accept at a 5% level of significance, else reject, is the decision criteria for the null hypothesis.

Granger Causality Test: This is conducted for the purpose of determining the extent to which the dependent variables and each of the explanatory variables do support or promote themselves in the growth process, granger causality will be executed to determine whether the variation in one variable (X) is caused by variation in another variable (y). Also to ascertain the extent to which they significantly support or promote each other in the economic growth process in the light of the inclusion of lag of the time series (Granger, 1981). A variable granger causes another if the F-statistic is significant at a p-value of 5% or less.

$$AP_t = w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^j \vartheta_i ACGS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^j \varpi_i MC_{jt-i} + \sum_{i=1}^j \varphi_i ADB_{jt-i} + \sum_{i=1}^j \vartheta_i BI_{jt-i} + \sum_{i=1}^j \varpi_i CB_{jt-i} + \mu_{1t} \quad (11)$$

It is important to note that the statement “x Granger causes y” does not imply that y is the effect or the result of x. Granger causality measures precedence and information content but does not by itself indicate causality in the more common use of the term. The reported F-statistics are the Wald statistics for the joint hypothesis that the coefficients on the lagged values of the other variable are zero for each equation. The F-statistics is the Wald statistics for the null hypothesis. If the F-statistics is greater than a certain critical value for an F distribution, then we reject the null hypothesis that Y does not Granger-cause X, which means that Y Granger-causes X.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This section provides in detail the analysis of data used in the study and interpretation of the empirical results. The source of data was from the Central Bank of Nigerian (CBN) statistical bulletin.

Table 1: ADF Unit root Test

Variable	ADF Stat	MacKinno 1%	5%	10%	Prob.	Order of integration
AP	-8.003915	-3.646342	-2.954021	-2.615817	0.0000	1(1)
ACGS	-5.923445	-3.646342	-2.954021	-2.615817	0.0000	1(1)
MC	-3.374622	-3.639407	-2.951125	-2.614300	0.0191	1(1)
ADB	-5.711991	-3.653730	-2.957110	-2.617434	0.0000	1(1)
BI	-6.303434	-3.670170	-2.963972	-2.621007	0.0000	1(1)
CB	-7.981873	-3.646342	-2.954021	-2.615817	0.0000	1(1)

Source: Author's Computations using E-Views 12.0

From results, the results of the unit root tests show that the null hypotheses of a unit root for time-dependent variables of a non-stationary nature can be made stationary at the first difference. It also shows that all the variables are integrated of order 1(1), this informed the adoption of Johansen Co-Integration Test. Having established the order of integration for the variables, the next step is to carry out a co-integration test to determine whether a long-run

relationship exists between the variables. In this study we adopted co-integration test developed by Johansen (1988).

Table 2: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.765612	110.0766	95.75366	0.0036
At most 1*	0.641000	96.55337	69.81889	0.0086
At most 2*	0.562405	75.82036	47.85613	0.0355
At most 3	0.174367	11.02655	29.79707	0.9605
At most 4	0.159203	5.278407	15.49471	0.7786
At most 5	0.002539	0.076264	3.841466	0.7824

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.765612	43.52327	40.07757	0.0197
At most 1*	0.641000	80.73301	33.87687	0.0134
At most 2*	0.562405	54.79381	27.58434	0.0093
At most 3	0.174367	5.748147	21.13162	0.9874
At most 4	0.159203	5.202142	14.26460	0.7162
At most 5	0.002539	0.076264	3.841466	0.7824

Source: Author's Computations using E-Views 12.0

Johansen co-integration test determines whether the long-term relationship occurs in variables or not. The test envisages that there can be just one relationship between variables in long term. In most cases, if two variables that are I(1) are linearly combined, the combination will also be I(1). More generally, if variables with differing orders of integration are combined, then the combination will have an order of integration equal to the largest. Johansen-Juselius Cointegration tests are presented in the tables above where the result shows that the variables are cointegrated and significant at the 5% level. Thus, these results suggest that a long run and stable relationship between the variables exists. The maximum Eigen and the trace statistics in the above table show the presence of one co-integrating equation at 5% significant level, which is an indication that there is a long run relationship among the variables.

Table 3: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
ACGS does not Granger Cause AP	30	3.30949	0.0366
AP does not Granger Cause ACGS		0.39848	0.6755
MC does not Granger Cause AP	30	1.05788	0.3622
AP does not Granger Cause MC		0.41306	0.6661
ADB does not Granger Cause AP	30	0.20196	0.8184
AP does not Granger Cause ADB		0.58871	0.5626
BI does not Granger Cause AP	30	0.44572	0.6454
AP does not Granger Cause BI		1.66273	0.2099
CB does not Granger Cause AP	30	1.61282	0.2194
AP does not Granger Cause CB		0.25289	0.7785

According to the results of the analysis, granger causality runs uni-directionally from agricultural credit grantee scheme to agricultural productivity. Hence, this relationship is one-sided in nature. It can also be inferred that agricultural productivity does not granger causes agricultural credit grantee scheme. Other variables have no causal relationship existing between.

Table 4: Error Correction Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.		
D(AP (-1))	-0.224556	0.316619	-0.709233	0.4891		
D(ACGS (-1))	0.575547	0.279140	2.061861	0.0470		
D(ACGS(-2))	0.005883	0.030867	0.190583	0.8514		
D(MC (-1))	0.278172	0.237305	1.972215	0.0494		
D(ADB (-1))	0.233064	0.361307	0.645057	0.5286		
D(ADB (-2))	0.150230	0.270230	0.555936	0.5865		
D(BI (-1))	0.440469	0.236461	1.862753	0.0422		
D(BI (-2))	0.050007	0.037938	1.318123	0.2072		
D(CB (-1))	-0.136354	0.224233	-0.608089	0.5522		
D(CB (-2))	-0.622102	0.291047	-2.137460	0.0494		
C	4.518553	3.396853	1.330217	0.2033		
ECM(-1)	-1.528238	0.484789	-3.152378	0.0066		
R-squared	0.802702	Mean dependent var		0.716897		
Adjusted R-squared	0.631710	S.D. dependent var		28.51370		
S.E. of regression	17.30408	Akaike info criterion		8.846034		
Sum squared resid	4491.470	Schwarz criterion		9.506108		
Log likelihood	-114.2675	Hannan-Quinn criter.		9.052761		
F-statistic	4.694387	Durbin-Watson stat		1.784002		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002805					
VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria						
Endogenous variables: ACGSMCADBBICB						
Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-812.2840	NA	1.30e+17	56.43338	56.71627	56.52198
1	-759.9996*	79.32809*	4.48e+16*	55.31032*	57.29054*	55.93050*
2	-714.2473	50.48530	3.26e+16	54.63774	58.31530	55.78951
3	-611.7360	70.69746	1.03e+15	50.05076	55.42564	51.73410

Source: Author's Computations using E-Views 12.0

The existence of cointegration among the variables allows us to implement the Error Correction Modeling technique, which describes the systematic disequilibrium adjustment process and the short-run transmission mechanism between development finance and productivity of agricultural sector. The result of the ECM is presented in Table 4.5 above. We observe that the estimated lagged error-correction term (ECMt-1) emerges as an important channel of influence. The statistically significant error-correction term, confirms the existence of long run relationships between development finance and agricultural productivity. In other words, the series quickly adjusts to eliminate any deviations from the long-run equilibrium relationships that they may share with each other. It is evidence that the coefficient of ECM prove that the variables can adjust at the speed of 153 percent. The independent variables 63.1 percent variation in productivity of the agricultural sector, the model is statistically significant by the value of f-probability. The study found at lag I that agricultural credit grantee scheme has positive and significant effect on the productivity of agricultural sector, microcredit have positive and significant effect on agricultural productivity, agricultural development bank have positive but no significant effect, bank of industry have positive and significant effect while commercial bank credit have negative and no significant effect on productivity of the sector within the periods of the study.

Discussion of Findings

Agricultural Credit Grantee Scheme: The formulated model found that the Agricultural Credit Grantee Scheme has a positive and significant effect on the productivity of the agricultural sector within the periods of this study. The model results found that a unit increase in Agricultural Credit Grantee Scheme added a 0.5 percent increase in the productivity of the agricultural sector. The positive and significant effect of the Agricultural Credit Grantee Scheme is expected and confirms the objective of the credit scheme. The

findings are in line with Egwu (2016), who found that Commercial Bank Credit to the Agricultural Sector (CBCA) and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund Loans to Nigeria's Agricultural Sector (ACGSF) indicated significance in Agricultural Sector Output as a Percentage of GDP (ASOGDP); Oyeronke and Bolarinwa (2017), who reported that only 21.4 percent of the total number of farmers have access to ACGSF loans. In addition, the majority of the credit fund is allocated to food crop cultivation. The study suggests that agricultural policies be improved in order to establish a favourable and enabling environment for farmers, particularly small-scale farmers, to obtain finance; Odetola and Etumnu (2013) found that the agriculture sector's crop production subsector and GDP progress are mutually beneficial.

Microcredit: The estimated model found that micro credit from the microfinance banks has positive and significant effect on the productivity of agricultural sector in Nigeria. The estimated model found that microcredit added 0.27 percent to agricultural productivity over the periods of the study. The positive effect of microcredit on the productivity of agricultural sector confirms the a-priori expectation of the study and supports the financial intermediation theory. The positive findings are in line with the findings of Mbelu and Ifionu (2022) that agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund shows a positive and significant influence on the gross domestic product in Nigeria, the findings of Olatunji et al. (2018) that agricultural credit, money markets, capital markets, and exchange rates have a positive relationship with agricultural growth in Nigeria. Enoma (2010) found that in Nigeria, agricultural finance, interest rates, and exchange rates stimulate output from the evaluation of the impact of agriculture credit on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986-2007. Okosodo (2016) found that government expenditure in the agricultural sector has a positive impact on the performance of the Nigerian economy and the findings of Nwankwo (2013) found that there is agricultural financing promotes the expansion of the Nigerian economy significantly, but that the rate of loan repayment has had a detrimental impact on the increase of the Nigerian economy over time.

Agricultural Development Bank: The study found that Agricultural Development Bank finance has positive but no significant effect on the productivity of agricultural sector in Nigeria. From the findings, Agricultural Development Bank finance added 0.23 percent to productivity of agricultural sector. The positive effect of Agricultural Development Bank finance confirms the expectations of the study and is in line with financial intermediation theory. Empirically, the positive effect of Agricultural Development Bank finance confirms the empirical findings of Omosebi and Aladejana (2016) that agricultural finance and economic growth have a strong short- and long-term correlation. Adetiloye (2012) found that credit to the agricultural sector has a positive effect on economic productivity but is inconsequential to the economy in terms of growth, whereas ACGSF indicated an adverse performance on economic growth. The findings of Tihamiyu et al. (2017) and the findings of Ali et al. (2016) show that deposit money banks' credit is significant for output leap in the agricultural sector (AQ).

Bank of Industry: The study established that finance from bank of industry have positive and significant effect on the productivity of agricultural sector. The estimated model found bank of industry finance added 0.4 percent to the productivity of agricultural sector. The positive effect of finance from bank of industry confirms the a-priori expectations of the study and is in line with financial intermediation theory. The findings are in line with the findings of Nwakamma et al. (2014) that the number of microcredit products be increased in order to accelerate microcredit's contribution to Nigeria's economic growth. The findings of

Medugui et al. (2019) show that commercial bank credit as well as government expenditure on agriculture predicts output level in Nigeria. Olorunsola et al. (2017) found that there is no evidence of short-term and long-term disunity between loan and output lump in the agricultural sector. Hence, suggested that the policy on agric sector credit moratoriums should be enhanced, and the findings of Obansa and Maduekwe (2013) show that foreign direct private loans, share capital, foreign direct investment, and development stocks can boost productivity, while the capital-output ratio is enhanced and financed by multilateral loans and domestic savings.

Commercial Banks Credit: The estimated model found that commercial banks credit has negative and no significant effect on the productivity of agricultural sector. The model found a unit increase in commercial banks credit reduced agricultural productivity within the periods under study. The negative effect of commercial banks credit contradicts the a-priori expectation and failed to confirm financial intermediation theory. The negative effect of commercial banks credit could be as a result of poor lending to the agricultural sector. A critical examination of Central Bank of Nigeria Report showed that commercial banks credit to agricultural sector to total credit falls below 10 percent between the periods covered in this study, this might be as a result of the perceived credit risk in the sector. The findings confirm the findings of Saka, Akindeand Afolabi (2023) that DMBs loans and advances have significantly negative short-run impacts on agricultural development in Nigeria at both aggregate and sub-sector levels. But confirm the findings of Osabohien et al., (2020) that increased access to bank credit facilities significantly and positively improve the performance of Nigeria agricultural sector in the long run and the findings of Ezu (2023) that Bank of Agriculture credit to farmers as well as commercial banks credit to agriculture showed a significant relationship to Gross Domestic Product.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The main focus of this study is on the long-term impact of development finance on the productivity of Nigeria's agricultural sector. The research spans the years 1990 through 2023. The agricultural credit guarantee scheme, microcredit, agricultural development bank, bank of industry and commercial banks finance were used. The unit root test, co-integration test, error correction model, and granger causality test are all part of the study's methodology. At the initial difference, all of the variables used were stationary. A long-term relationship exists. The long-run relationship showed that all of the variables used during the study period had a positive and efficient impact on agricultural productivity except commercial banks credit. Furthermore, the speed at which agricultural productivity disequilibrium is being corrected is 115 percent while the granger causality flows from agricultural credit grantee scheme to agricultural productivity.

Recommendations

- i. The study recommends that Government should continually increase the funding and operation of the agriculture credit guarantee scheme fund, reduction of monetary policy rate on the agricultural sector and that Central Bank of Nigeria should mandate commercial bank to set aside a certain amount of money from their yearly profit to finance agriculture.
- ii. The study recommends that there is need for agricultural policy makers and governments in Nigeria to develop appropriate specific agricultural financing

- mechanism that can aid performance of agricultural sector in the short-run and maintain long-run positive gains in the sector.
- iii. To foster productivity in Nigeria, the study recommends that agricultural development bank should increase the number of loan facilities mapped out for the agricultural sector.
 - iv. Federal government should motivate bank of industry to provide adequate credit facilities to the Agricultural sector through moderate bank lending rates for ease of farming business in Nigeria. Proactive campaigns on the availability of credit facilities for farmers to enable them to have access to loans at a single-digit interest rate. This could be achieved through social media, door-to-door vibes, town hall meetings and market squares. Government should create an enabling environment for farmers through the provision of adequate security, pest control measures and seedlings.
 - v. This study recommends that the monetary policy of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should further direct commercial banks and other financial institutions to lend to agricultural sector for better performance and there has been various government policies aimed to revamp the agricultural sector through deposit money banks financing, therefore there is need for better implementation of these agricultural policies to attract investment in the sector.

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